

Discovery of one 21-Digit Palindromic Prime in the Decimal Expansion of π

Franck Gobbo

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1 Introduction

On November 13, 2025, a computational search was conducted to identify palindromic prime numbers of length 21 within the $8 \times 10^{11} - 10^{12}$ - decimal digits of the mathematical constant π (approximately 3.141592653589793238462643383...). Using a modified C program with streaming capabilities to handle a 200 GB file containing the decimal expansion of π , one palindromic prime were discovered. A palindromic prime is a number that is both a palindrome (reads the same forwards and backwards) and a prime number. This document presents the positions of this palindrome in the decimal expansion of π . The detailed results, including certificate of primality and a confirmation of the absolute position using DigitViewer, are available on ZENODO.

2 Results

The following list enumerates the palindromic prime of length 21 found in the decimal expansion of π , along with its starting and ending positions (1-based indexing, relative to the first decimal digit after the decimal point in π):

1. **Palindrome: 359342190050091243953**
Positions: 880347462679-880347462699

3 Methodology

The search was performed using a custom C program employing the GMP library for arbitrary-precision arithmetic and multi-threading for efficiency. The program processed a 200 GB file containing 2×10^{11} decimal digits of π , using a streaming approach to minimize memory usage. The search targeted palindromes of length 21 within the interval $[8 \times 10^{11} - 10^{12}]$, the search duration was approximately 120 minutes. The certificate of primality for the discovered palindrome is archived on ZENODO for public access.